

Titrimetric Determination of Thorium(IV) using N-(2-Hydroxyethyl)ethylenediaminetriacetic Acid as Titrant and Pyrocatechol Violet as an Indicator

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Thorium(IV) has been determined by visual titration with N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-ethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) around pH 2.5, using pyrocatechol violet (PCV) as an indicator at room temperature. The colour change is from pink to lemon-yellow. The optimum range for the estimation was found to be 6.0 μg to 1.19 mg Th per ml in a total volume of 75 ml. The relative standard deviation for 16 samples in 2 different concentrations (i.e. 6.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ to 63 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ Th in the optimum range) was found to be in the range of 1.3% to 0.45%. The optimum conditions like pH, concentration of HEDTA, concentration of indicator, temperature were also established and described. The interference of foreign ions was also studied and their tolerance limits were established and described.

TITRIMETRIC methods for the determination of thorium are not many. In the earlier methods disodium salt of EDTA was used as titrant^{1,2}. Apart from EDTA, nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA)³ and disodium salt of anthranilic-N,N-diacetic acid (ANDA)⁴, *trans*-1,2-diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic acid (DCTA)⁵ and triethylenetetraminehexaacetic acid (TTHA)⁶ were also introduced for the titration of thorium with some indicators. In our comparative study of various titrants for the titrimetric determination of thorium using various indicators and titrants, we studied HEDTA as a titrant and pyrocatechol violet as an indicator.

Experimental

Thorium(IV) solution: A 0.1 M solution of thorium nitrate $[\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (Fischer Scientific Co., USA) was prepared with a few drops of nitric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of thorium and was standardized gravimetrically by the conventional benzoic acid method⁷.

HEDTA solution: A 0.1 M solution of HEDTA (Aldrich Chemical Company, Inc., USA) was prepared in distilled water with a few drops of sodium hydroxide to give a clear solution.

Pyrocatechol violet (PCV) (GR): A 0.1% aqueous solution of PCV (Loba. Chem. Industrial Co., Bombay) was prepared.

All other solutions were prepared from A. R. quality reagents in distilled water.

Procedure: The solution of thorium(IV) is diluted until it contains 0.4468-89.36 mg of the metal per 75 ml of solution (i.e. 0.0059 mg/ml-1.19 mg/ml). The pH is adjusted to 2.3-3.0 and 3 drops of the PCV solution is added. This is

titrated with 0.01 M solution of HEDTA until the colour changes from pink to lemon-yellow.

One ml of 0.01 M HEDTA is equal to 2.321 mg of Th.

Results and Discussion

pH variation: Two ml of 0.1 M solution of thorium(IV) was taken and diluted to 75 ml, pH adjusted to different value between 1.0 and 3.5, and it was found that the end point was sharp between 2.3 to 3.0. Below this pH range the end point was not observed at all and above this pH range the precipitation of thorium(IV) was observed. Between pH 2.3 and 3.0, the results were accurate and reproducible. In all further experiments pH was maintained at 2.5 ± 0.1 .

HEDTA variation: HEDTA concentration was varied from 0.001 M to 0.1 M while titrating 2.0 ml of thorium(IV) (4.46 mg Th in 75 ml) (i.e. 0.059 mg/ml) at pH 2.5. It was observed that 0.01 M HEDTA is the best concentration of the titrant that can be used. In other cases the error was slightly more. So in all further studies the titration was performed with 0.01 M HEDTA only.

Indicator variation: Indicator was varied from 1 to 10 drops of 0.1% solution and it was found that in all cases the end point was sharp. 3 drops of indicator is sufficient to judge the end point with the naked eye easily. Hence in further titrations only 3 drops of indicator (0.1% solution) was added.

Temperature study: The end point as described above was sharp even at room temperature throughout the thorium(IV) concentration range estimated. Above and below the range mentioned, the end point was not sharp. At much higher concentrations of thorium(IV) the titration could be

carried out if the temperature near the end point is maintained at 50°. But it was felt unnecessary to go for higher concentrations of thorium(IV) as at room temperature the end point was sharp with lower concentrations of thorium.

Range, relative standard deviation According to the procedure described above the optimum concentration of thorium(IV) that can be titrated was found to be 0.059 mg/ml-1.19 mg/ml (in a total volume of 75 ml). Below and above this range the end point was not sharp. Relative standard deviation of 16 samples in 2 different concentrations of thorium in the optimum range was found to be in the range of 1.3% to 0.45%.

Effect of foreign ions: The following foreign ions do not show any significant error in the estimation of 1.16 mg of thorium in 75 ml according to the procedure described above.

K(I) 2000.0 mg (1818 times); Ba(II) 2000.0 mg (1818 times); Mn(II) 1000.0 mg (909 times); Sr(II) 1000.0 mg (909 times); Mg(II) 500.0 mg (454.5 times); Ca(II) 480.0 mg (436.3 times); U(VI) 150.0 mg (136.3 times); Cr(III) 60.0 mg (54.5 times); Cd(II) 40.0 mg (36.3 times); Pb(II) 26.0 mg (23.6 times); rare earths(III) 25.0 mg (22.7 times); Al(III) 20.0 mg (18.0 times); Cu(II) 5.0 mg (4.5 times). However Zr(IV), Fe(III), Sn(II) and Ti(IV) cause serious interference even if present at 1.0 mg level and should be eliminated before titration.

Among the anions fluoride, sulphate, phosphate and oxalate cause serious interferences. Nitrate and chloride do not interfere at all.

Thorium(IV) forms a pink coloured complex with PCV at pH 2.0-3.0 and by treatment with HEDTA this pink colour is changed to lemon-yellow around pH 2.5. This reaction has been utilized for the titrimetric determination of thorium using PCV as indicator. Since the titration is carried out in an acidic solution comparatively few cations form complexes with HEDTA of sufficient strength to interfere. Thorium can be estimated in presence of the above mentioned foreign ions.

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